

Original Research

Cocoa Production and Rural Livelihood Outcomes: A Sustainable Livelihood Framework and Binary Regression Analysis among Smallholder Farmers

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Received 3 November 2025 Revised 14 December 2025 Accepted 17 December 2025

Abstract

The study assessed the effect of cocoa production on the livelihoods of smallholder farmers in Kyela district in Mbeya region. The study employed a cross-sectional design in the collection of data from the sample of 334 smallholder farmers. A stratified sampling technique was used in the sampling of respondents whereby the proportion random sampling was used in selecting respondents. The Binary logistic regression was used to analyse the effects of cocoa production on the farmers' livelihoods. Findings indicated that improvement in farmers' livelihoods were highly enhanced by education (0.74, $p = 0.001$), quantity produced (0.65, $p = 0.003$) and size of land (0.51, $p = 0.010$). Similarly, access to credit, market price and ownership of farm equipment by farmers indicated to have positive significant association with the farmers' livelihood. This implies that provision of more knowledge and expanding land size accompanied by access to financial resource could increase the possibility of improving the livelihoods of smallholder farmers. The study concludes that, access to financial, human and physical resources improves the livelihoods of farmers in the district. Thus, more investment in education and strategies aiming at increasing the market access in term of process and financial resources will enable farmers to produce more and earn income to improve their livelihoods.

Keywords: Cocoa production, effects, livelihoods, smallholder farmers, Tanzania.

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Introduction

Cocoa production plays a crucial role in improving the livelihoods of smallholder farmers. The crop serves as a significant source of income, enabling farmers to meet basic needs, invest in education, and improve their living standards (Mhando, 2023; URT, 2022). Worldwide, the cocoa industry has been a major contributor to the improvements for the livelihoods of millions of smallholder farmers. As noted by Wessel & Quist-Wessel (2020) that, cocoa farming significantly affects livelihood outcomes, contributing to improved household income and food security. The increased income from cocoa production could increase the farmers' access to agricultural inputs, education and healthcare. For example, in the season 2023/2024, Africa produced 3.2 MT which accounts for more than 70% of the world's cocoa production led by Côte d'Ivoire in which about 5 million households rely on cocoa farming as their primary source of income (ICCO, 2025; Amegbe, 2023; Yiridomoh et al., 2022). Despite cocoa being a lucrative commodity, many smallholder farmers still live in poverty streams in many cocoa producing countries (Adams & Carodenuto, 2023). This argument was evidenced by findings from previous studies (Oomes et al., 2016; Fountain & Huetz-Adams, 2020) who reported that about 40% of cocoa farmers in Côte d'Ivoire were living below the poverty line. The ICCO (2025) in support of this argument, projected a 10% decline in cocoa production among major cocoa producers in Africa in the season of 2025/2026 due to climate change and poor farming practices. This indicates that, the contribution of the crop in improving the livelihoods for majority of people in developing countries is limited especially in Africa where production is carried out under subsistence system.

In developed countries, cocoa production is often more mechanized as compared to developing countries, with farmers having better access to technology and improved inputs, leading to higher yields and better farmers' income. For instance, in the United States, where cocoa is a minor agricultural activity, cocoa farmers have better access to market information which makes them to produce product of higher quality and profit margins. Additionally, findings from previous studies indicated that, producers in developed countries are often part of certified supply chains which contributes to farmers' better prices and conditions (Hainmueller, Hiscox, & Tampe, 2021; Wessel & Quist-Wessel, 2015). In contrast, smallholder cocoa farmers in developing countries such as in West Africa, Latin America, and Asia are still facing numerous challenges, including low productivity, poor access to markets, and volatile cocoa prices (Anang et al., 2022; Yiridomoh et al., 2022). The similar situation was observed in Ghana whereby cocoa production experienced a 5% decline in 2022 due to disease outbreaks and poor weather conditions despite of being the second-largest cocoa producer globally after Côte d'Ivoire (ICCO, 2022). The decrease in cocoa production was reported to impact farmers' incomes and livelihoods in the country, making smallholder farmers in Ghana earn less than \$1 per day, far below the international poverty line despite the government's efforts to improve the sector (Hejkrlik & Amegbe, 2023). This implies that, contribution of cocoa production on the farmers' livelihoods is limited due to poor farming technologies and practices.

Cocoa production in Tanzania, remains relatively small compared to leading African producers such as Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana. But it still a crucial livelihood activity for smallholder farmers in the country, particularly in the Kyela District of the Mbeya

Region. However, the report of Tanzania Agricultural Development Bank (2025) cocoa production in Kyela has experienced fluctuating trends over the past three years with the decline by 5% in 2023 due to adverse weather conditions and pest infestations. Despite these challenges, cocoa continues to be a vital source of income for the majority of local farmers in the district, who depend on it for their economic well-being (Tanzania Agricultural Development Bank (TADB), 2025; URT, 2022). Moreover, Tanzanian cocoa farmers face several persistent obstacles that hinder productivity and profitability. One of the most pressing issues is the inefficiency of the cocoa value chain which make farmers to receive only about 60% of the final market price, largely due to the presence of multiple intermediaries along the value chain (Lazaro & Makindara, 2020; Msuya & Adolwa, 2021). Hence, solving these structural hindrances are key to improving the standard of living and realizing the full capacity of cocoa farming in the district.

Many challenges still threaten the cocoa value chain in Tanzania, with very dire consequences to the smallholder farmers livelihoods, with Kyela District not being spared. These comprise poor productivity as a result of archaic farming practices, less access to credit and extension services, and the effect of climate change that is worsening crop diseases while diminishing yield. For example, Lazaro and Makindara (2020) have found that smallholder cocoa farmers in Kyela district continue to encounter difficulties in accessing markets which deprive them the opportunity of obtaining fair prices and attaining sustainability production thereby leading to low returns from their crops hence poor food security. Moreover, Msuya and Adolwa (2021) emphasized that pest and disease attacks on cocoa in Tanzania are having a negative effect on production and this largely side-lines smallholder growers.

In response to these challenges, the Tanzanian government is developing some of the smallholder farming projects in several parts of the country. For instance, the Government has encouraged new high-quality cocoa varieties and offered technical training on sustainable agriculture practices which enhanced cocoa production by 15% in these factories' farmers-main producer areas- Mbeya and Morogoro (Ministry of Agriculture, 2022). The cooperative societies have also provided a way of securing better markets for the farmers, with about 25% of the smallholder cocoa farmers benefitting from such societies (URT, 2022). All these undertakings were to enhance cocoa production and incomes.

However, in the context of Kyela district in Tanzania, yet such initiatives are very little and livelihood status for cocoa smallholder farmers is still unsustainable. A lot of farmers still face low productivity and lack of access to market and still have price volatility for cocoa that has a negative impact on their income and livelihood. For example, a recent study by Mhando (2023) shows that only 30% of cocoa farmers in Kyela district have attained livelihoods above the poverty level. Moreover, the failure to provide enough infrastructure and accessible credit facilities has made it difficult for farmers invest in better farming technology and practices which could have further reduce their vulnerability to livelihood risks (Ngole, 2021). The proliferation of the poverty condition among smallholder framers in the district despite the multiple government interventions aimed at improving farmers' livelihoods rises critical questions about the underlying factors that sustain this condition. Why these conditions persist and what should be done to improve the situations. To address knowledge gap, scientifically

generated evidences is imperatively that can will help to inform the government and policy makers to design an effective and context-specific interventions for eliminating the problem. To draw a viable conclusion, the study was guided by the assumption that the persistent of the poverty among cocoa farmers can be linked to various structural and socioeconomic factors. Specifically, the study hypothesis that low adoption of improved agricultural technologies and limited access to credit are critical determinants to persistent poverty among famers in the study area (H1).

Previous researches on cocoa production in Tanzania and beyond has primarily focused on the technical aspects of production, such as improving yields and pest control measures Msuya and Adolwa (2021). Few studies examined the economic impact of cocoa farming on the livelihoods of farmers such as those of Mwambene (2021) and Matango (2022), but have not fully addressed the sustainability of these livelihoods, particularly in the context of changing market dynamics and climate change. Similarly, there is limited research on the socio-economic impact of cocoa production on smallholder farmers' livelihoods, particularly in specific regions like Kyela District. This gap in the literature and the persistence increase in poverty motivated the current study to explore the impact of cocoa production on smallholder farmers' livelihoods in Kyela District, Mbeya. Therefore, this study assessed the effects of cocoa production on the livelihoods of farmers in Kyela district using sustainable livelihood approach in a rural context. Understanding these effects is crucial for designing interventions that can improve the well-being of farmers and the sustainability of cocoa production in the region and the country at large.

Theoretical Literature Review

Livelihood Framework Theory

The study was framed using Sustainable Livelihood Framework developed in 1992 by Chambers and Conway, upgraded by DFID UK (1999) and Dorward *et al.* (2003) by incorporating markets, institutions and technology in the context of poverty alleviation initiatives in rural areas. It is a theoretical framework that explains the poor people or households in rural areas make their living based on assets and activities. It posits that livelihoods are built on five different forms of capital assets (human, social, financial, natural and physical) in an interactive process with the external environment including policies, institutions and vulnerability contexts (see Figure 1). The logic is that the sustainability of livelihoods is depending on farmer's ability to access and utilize those assets, managing risks, economies or environment changes to operate effectively. Kedah (2013) further suggests that the theory is appropriate in this kind of study since it aims to understand the enhanced livelihood among smallholder farmers whose life revolves around farming production for income.

One of the strengths of the Livelihood Framework is that it can take a holistic approach to assess the complex nature of livelihoods by taking various dimensions into consideration (social, economic and ecological) (Carney, 1998; Scoones, 1998). This makes it useful to look at the nexus between cocoa production and livelihood assets among smallholder farmers in Kyela District. It is also responsive to different

environmental settings thus flexible in analyzing different livelihoods strategies and outcomes (Ellis, 2000; Ellis & Mdoe, 2003).

By considering the way in which cocoa farming impacts livelihood assets and affects outcomes in terms of income, education and food security, the framework also contributes to understanding how external factors such as market access and institutional support condition those endowments. (Chambers & Conway, 1992; Scoones, 1998). It also has the potential to underscore cocoa farmer vulnerability to climate change and price instability which can aid in recommendations for policy interventions which aim to enhance sustainability and resilience (Natarajan et al., 2022). As such, smallholder cocoa farmers in Kyela will rely of how they capitalize the five assets to generate income for life well-being in order to live.

Figure 1: The Sustainable Livelihood Framework
 Source: Modified from Natarajan et al. (2022) in DFID (1999)

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework provides the contribution of independent variables on the livelihoods of smallholder farmers in the study area. Availability of livelihood assets such financial capital (income and savings), human capital (skills and education), and physical capital (farm tools and infrastructure) to households facilitated the enhancement of cocoa farmers to improve their livelihoods (Donkor et al., 2023). The ownership of these assets provides the foundation for reducing vulnerability and thus promoting economic resilience among cocoa farmers (Hejkrlik & Amegbe, 2023). Smallholder farmers' livelihoods is the dependent variable measured by household income which presents the

overall well-being and economic stability of farmers in Kyela District. According to Resell & Prestegard (2024) noted that the improvement in household livelihoods is related to the increase in livelihood assets the household access. Therefore, in this study it was assumed that increase in availability of livelihood assets among cocoa farmers will contribute on the improvement in farmers' livelihoods. This conceptual framework aligns with the sustainable livelihood framework approach, thus provides a basis for analyzing how cocoa production supports livelihood improvements within the local context.

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework of the study

Contribution of cocoa production to livelihoods among cocoa farmers

About 78% of the global cocoa production originated from only five key producing countries namely Cote d'Ivoire, Ghana, Ecuador, Indonesia and Brazil (Olutosin Ademola Otekunrin, 2025). In these countries, cocoa production is critical as it has an impact on accumulation of a pool of livelihood assets, which are key for enhancing smallholder farmer well-being. Among these assets are financial, physical, human and natural capital (Lazaro & Makidara, 2020). Effective utilization of these assets with the interaction of market accessibility are thought to improve livelihoods through increased per capital income. This argument was supported by finding from study by Adu et al. (2021) that earnings from cocoa farming are largely used as financial capital, which cater to immediate family needs and future investments. Cocoa growing households around the world invest their cocoa income to buy livestock, farm machinery and improve home infrastructure (better housing or irrigation) (Asare *et al.*, 2020). Cocoa production also creates monetary capital, which many farmers use to expand farm size or buy inputs such as fertilizer and land in the areas of cocoa production. All of these depict the significance

of cocoa production in the income generation and general well-being of global communities.

Cocoa farming continues to be a potential source of financial capital for the most smallholder farmers in Africa. Data from FAO (2025) confirmed that Ivory coast maintained the leading position in cocoa production in Africa followed by Ghana in 2023. In Ghana for stance, cocoa farmers are engaged in the conversion of their income into other livelihood assets; a practice which is typified by availing themselves new physical assets like tractors, farm tools and facilities (Adu *et al.*, 2021). With this investment they can produce more cocoa and that means greater productivity and income in the long term for farmers. In the same vein, increased per capital income from cocoa contributes to better access to education and enhanced health status among cocoa growing households in Ghana (Adu *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, a number of farmers do use cocoa income to purchase animals and these contribute additional revenue as well as boost their cash asset base and hence resilience to financial or environmental shocks. For example, in Cote d'Ivoire, cocoa incomes are utilized by farmers to invest into their physical capital such as land or improved farming tools to increase agricultural productivity (Asare *et al.*, 2020). Others, however, invest their income from cocoa in home improvement and children's education (Akpomuvie *et al.*, 2019). These physical capital investments are benefiting farmers to improve their lives, increase productivity and develop additional incomes. The economic values of farming cocoa generally go a long way to uplift the standard of living of households in farming cocoa (Akpomuvie *et al.*, 2019). This is because increase in income associated with increase in purchasing power of farmer toward improved agricultural inputs and technologies.

Studies by Musoke *et al.* (2021) and Matango (2022) revealed that the smallholder cocoa farmers in the Uganda, Tanzania, and other East African countries also utilised income derived from cocoa into capital accumulation for bettering their livelihoods. In Uganda, for example, findings indicate that cocoa farmers are utilizing their income to purchase livestock that subsequently contribute to increased incomes and food. Cocoa producers also spend on multifaceted education and health that enhances their human capital, thereby improving their total livelihood conditions.

Likewise, in Tanzania farmers especially in Kyela District earn cocoa income to buy farm inputs, renovate houses and improve the quality of education for their children as well as health facilities access, which contributes towards improving physical and human capital (Ngowi *et al.* 2020). Revenue derived from the sale of cocoa allows farmers to lead a better life as well as have easier access to necessary goods and services. TADB (2025) reported that TZ in 2023 exported 12,162 tonnes of raw or roasted cocoa beans worth USD 39 million. This means Tanzania still have another potential to increase the cocoa production to satisfy the current world market's needs. Therefore, the critical role of cocoa production in supporting income improvement and sustaining livelihoods among rural households in Tanzania particularly in Kyela has prompted the need for this study.

Despite extensive studies on cocoa production and its influence on farmer livelihoods in various regions, significant research gaps remain concerning its specific impacts on smallholder farmers in Kyela district, Mbeya. Studies by Ngole, (2021) and Hejkrlik and Amegbe (2023), reported smallholder farmers livelihoods in many parts of Tanzania

including Kyela district still lacking access to credit facilities and improved infrastructures limiting the ability of farmers to invest in improved farming practices, thus, further exacerbating their vulnerabilities to poverty. Additionally, Mhando (2023) reported that only 30% of cocoa farmers in Kyela district managed to achieve a livelihood above the poverty line, majority still live under poverty line. Therefore, need for studies focusing on the specific region or district to uncover the hidden circumstances among smallholder farmers is imperative. This will help the study to come with evidences to answer the current hypothesis that increase in cocoa production directly related to the improvement in the livelihood outcomes among smallholder farmers in Kyela district.

Research Methodology

Study Area and Research Design

This study was conducted in Kyela District, Mbeya Region located in the Southern Highland of Tanzania, focusing on the three wards of Matema, Mbabu, and Makwale, which were recognized as the largest producers of cocoa in the district. Kyela District was chosen due to its favorable climatic conditions and fertile volcanic soils making it one of the leading cocoa-producing areas in Tanzania, contributing approximately 33% of the national cocoa production followed by Morogoro region (Matango, 2022; URT, 2022). However, despite these advantages, the district experienced a significant decline in cocoa production in recent years. For example, reports indicated that cocoa production in Kyela dropped by approximately 25% between 2018 and 2023, adversely affecting farmers' livelihoods. Many farmers faced reduced incomes, increasing their vulnerability to poverty and food insecurity. The district's strategic location near export routes added to its relevance, as understanding and addressing production challenges in this area had significant implications for both local and international cocoa markets (Msuya and Mdolwa, 2021; URT, 2020). This study adopted a cross-sectional research design, as it allowed the collection of data from the population at a specific point in time and enabled the researcher to draw conclusions based on that data.

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

Sample size determination

The sample size of the study was selected from the total population (N) of 2, 028 smallholder cocoa farmers in the selected three wards in Kyela District Council and calculated using the Yamane (1967) which is recommended for selecting sample size from the known population. The formula was presented in the following equation

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N \times e^2} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$n = \frac{2028}{1+2028 \times 0.05^2} \quad n = 334 \text{ respondents}$$

Where: n = sample size to be studied

N= population size (2,028)

e = margin of error (0.05)

Sampling procedures

The study employed a purposive sampling in selecting the area of study and key informants. These key informants were selected based on their expertise and positions in cocoa production. Key informants included district agricultural officers, Cooperative leaders, Ward and Village Executive Officers and farmer groups leaders. In selecting the respondents, a stratified sampling technique was used and involved in the study whereby farmers were categorized in different strata based on their ward and production. From each stratum, the simple proportion random sampling method was used in the selection of 334 smallholder cocoa farmers (Saunders *et al.* 2023; Kothari, 2009). The distribution of the sample size as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Sample size Estimation and distribution

Name of Ward	Total Population	Estimation of sample size	Sample Size
Matema	314	$314/2,028 \times 334$	51
Mbabu	684	$684/2,028 \times 334$	113
Makwale	1,030	$1,030/2,028 \times 334$	170
Total	2,028		334

Data Collection Methods

A survey method was employed in the collection of the relevant information in which the self-administered questionnaires with both open and close-ended questions were used in collecting the quantitative data from smallholder farmers to ensure comprehensive inclusion of necessary information. The inclusion of open-ended questions ensured that respondents had the freedom to provide detailed and nuanced answers while enabling the researcher to efficiently gather the required information with minimal effort. The questionnaire was designed and administered to a sample of 334 smallholder cocoa farmers from three selected wards in the Kyela District Council.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted to key informants which include ward extension officers, farmers leaders, cooperative leaders and district agriculture officer, ward and village executive officers purposively selected to gather information. The method used an interview guide as an appropriate tool for collecting information.

Data Analysis Methods

The study employed both descriptive and inferential analysis methods in analyzing the collected data. Collected data were first coded and analysed with the help of STATA computer software through which descriptive statistics and figures such as mean, standard deviations, percentage, table and charts were generated and used to present the descriptive results. On the other hand, the Binary logistic regression model was used in examining the effect of cocoa production to livelihood outcomes among cocoa farmers. The model was selected based on dependent variable (Livelihood) being a latent variable and therefore was dichotomized as (1= improved 0 = Not improved) based on the recommended minimum poverty line standard (above \$1) and for answering the research

question of whether livelihoods improved or not and ensure consistency in measurements. Also, the latent variable (Utility) in nature which fit for utility models like binary logistic. The equation is expressed in the following equation:

$$\text{Logit}(Y) = \ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + \beta_6X_6 + \beta_7X_7 + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

where $\ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \text{Log odds of improved livelihoods}$.

β_0 : Intercept term.

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6$ are coefficients of explaining the change in dependent variable

X_1 = Quantity of cocoa produced

X_2 = size of land owned and X_3 = price of cocoa per Kg, X_4 = Access to Credit, X_5 = Education level in years, X_6 = Ownership of farm tools, X_7 = Age of farmers
 ϵ : Error term.

Table 2 present the predicted effects of the independent variables on the farmers' livelihoods in the study area

Table 2: Expected sign of Effects on Livelihood of Variables include in the Model

Variable	Description of variable	Measurement	Expected Sign
Quantity of Cocoa produced	Annual amount of cocoa produced by farmers	Tones	Positive (+)
Size of Land	Land size allocated for cocoa cultivated by farmer in 2024	Ha	Positive (+)
Price of Cocoa	Average Market price received by farmer	TZS/Tones	Positive (+)
Access to Credit by farmers	Accessibility of farmers to financial services	Yes =1, No =2	Positive (+)
Education level of farmers	Level of education attained by farmer in years	Number of years in schooling	Positive (+)
Ownership of farm tools	Ownership of improved agricultural inputs (tractor or plough)	Yes = 1, No = 2	Positive (+)
Age of farmers	Age of cocoa farmers	Number of Years	Positive (+)

Furthermore, content analysis was used to analyze qualitative data from key informant interviews for all three objectives, and the findings from these sources were used to supplement quantitative findings from the questionnaires. To carry out the analysis, the

study established themes, transcribed the interview data, and compared the results with relevant theories and literature to enable better interpretation

Validity and Reliability testing

To ensure validity, this study employed evidence triangulation approach, collecting information from multiple sources to corroborate findings on the same fact or phenomenon. Moreover, a pre-testing of the data collection tools was conducted to detect and correct any potential problems that could restrict the instruments from successfully measuring their constructs. This technique increased the legitimacy of the study and retained that findings were grounded in respondents' environment and experiences (Bryman, 2012). Internal consistency of the measurement instruments was also tested using Cronbach's alpha. Cronbach's alpha has a value of 0 to 1 (Kothari, 2009; Saunders et al., 2009); and high values in the range from 0.7 to 1 mean that the measure here is highly reliable while low means there were inconsistencies as far as measuring intended constructs are concerned. The Cronbach's alpha reliability for this study ranged from was 0,81–0.881 which is more than the recommended value (0.70). This describes that the research instruments and results are reliable, which means that it validates to be credible (Table 3).

Table 3: Reliability Test

Variables	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha (α)
Livelihood activities	3	0.881
Livelihood asset	3	0.861
Cocoa production	3	0.801
Smallholder farmers' Livelihoods	2	0.831

Ethical consideration

The study adhered to all ethical principles in collecting the data as accurately as possible. Ethical clearance was obtained from relevant authorities; College of Business Education (CBE) region and Kyela administrative, Ward and Village Executive offices before conducting the study. Before engaging participants in the survey, we agreed on informed consent to take part and to understand what they were getting into as a study. Anonymity and confidentiality were assured in order to protect respondents' privacy. The research was conducted without causing harm, discrimination or coercions to the pregnant mothers and they participated on a voluntary basis. The study was also consistent with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee as well as with moral standards whenever applicable (Sources were cited properly and no plagiarism occurred in data analysis and reporting).

Results and Findings

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Understanding these characteristics is crucial for interpreting how personal and household attributes influence cocoa farming and livelihood outcomes. The analysis

includes gender, age, marital status, education level, and household size. These variables help contextualize the responses and patterns observed in subsequent sections of the study.

Table 4: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n = 334)

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	214	64.1
Female	120	35.9
Age Group		
18–30	76	22.8
31–40	98	29.3
41–50	90	26.9
51 and above	70	21.0
Marital Status		
Single	58	17.4
Married	232	69.5
Widowed	28	8.4
Divorced	16	4.8
Education Level		
No formal education	50	15.0
Primary	160	47.9
Secondary	90	26.9
College/University	34	10.2
Household Size		
1–3 Members	60	18.0
4–6 Members	190	56.9
7 and above	84	25.1

Results as presented in Table 4 indicate that, out of the 334 respondents, 64% were male while 36% were female. This suggests that cocoa farming in Kyela District is a male-dominated activity, due to cultural custom in Tanzania that exclude women in land ownership and labor allocation. The gender gap may reflect limited access by women to productive resources such as land and inputs. This demographic imbalance could influence the types of livelihood strategies adopted and the outcomes experienced.

The age distribution (Table 4) on the other hand, it shows that 29% of the interviewed respondents were aged at the age group of 31–40, followed by 26.9% aged 41–50, and 23% aged 18–30, while 21% were aged 51 and above. These findings reveal that the majority of cocoa farmers are in their productive and economically active years, suggesting a strong potential for farm labor availability and long-term sector sustainability. The dominance of the middle-aged group indicates continuity and experience in farming practices. This implies further that, the potentiality of cocoa production to improve the livelihood among farmers is high, if the available resources will be effectively utilized in the production and generate more income.

Similarly, about 69.5% of the smallholder farmers involved in the study were married, 17.4% single, 8.4% widowed, and only 4.8% were divorced. The high proportion of married individuals implies greater household responsibilities and possibly stronger reliance on agriculture as a primary livelihood.

About 89% them were uneducated or had less than primary education, 26.9%, 48%, and 15% had secondary school education, primary school education; some of them maybe not educated formally, 10.2% received the college/university as high qualification level respectively ($p < 0.001$). This suggests that a sizeable proportion of cocoa farmers have only very basic ability to read and write with limited or no advanced education which may be the basis of their restriction to easy understanding modern farming technology and financial literacy. Primary education would provide farmers with the capacity to absorb agricultural practices, secondary and high schooling also profitably lead to innovation and business management. Normally, educated farmers are knowledgeable on advance agricultural technologies and market information, such as price and customer.

Analysis shows that most respondents (56.9%) had households of 4–6 members, while 25.1% had 7 or more, and only 18% had 1–3 members. The larger household sizes imply more labor for cocoa farming household in one hand, but in other hand increase dependency and consumption needs. This dual effect has implications for productivity and income allocation. Oduro, Dzanku, and Alhassan (2021) observed, household size significantly affects labor distribution and income utilization in smallholder agricultural systems. In Kyela district, large household sizes could be both a resource and a burden, depending on how well household labor is managed and supported with farm income.

Descriptive Statistics for Livelihood Activities Performed by Smallholder Cocoa Farmers

Results in Table 5 indicate that, three core livelihood activity were commonly carried out by households in the district namely; agricultural practices, income-generating ventures, and household labor division. Among of the three livelihood activities, agriculture is conducted by the majority as presented by high mean (4.15), followed by household labour division (4.01) into various activities. Relative few households engaged in the income generating activities such business and trade. The high responses from respondents on farming practice, indicate that agriculture is the backbone for the economy and livelihoods of the majority smallholder farmers in Kyela districts. These results are in line with those presented in the report by Agricultural Non-State Actors Forum (2025), that about 65% households in Tanzania depend on agriculture for employment and their livelihoods.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics Results for Livelihood Activities (n=334)

Variables	Mean score	Standard deviations
Agriculture practices	4.15	0.82
Household labor division	4.01	0.79
Income-generating venture	3.92	0.88
Average Score	4.03	0.83

Results further suggests that cocoa production remains the primary livelihood base for smallholder farmers in Kyela, reinforcing its economic and social importance. The strong reliance on agriculture implies that interventions targeting improvement in cocoa productivity and input access can significantly improve household welfare in the district.

One agricultural extension officer verified these findings, saying that “*Cocoa farming is the lifestyle for almost all rural folks here. Even in the off-season, they work on their cocoa fields, or prepare land for intercropping.*” Another noted that “*Farmers in Kyela love cocoa so much, it is what they depend on for living*”.

These results are also consistent with those from Mhando (2023) who assured that majority of smallholder farmers in Kyela depend on cocoa as the chief enterprise and invest much of their effort and time to this cash crop because it has high-income potential. The adoption of agriculture as the primary livelihood strategy is the pillar of both income and food security in cocoa growing areas. Income diversified activities had a mean of 3.92 and a standard deviation of 0.88, implying that farmers to some extent diversify into non-farm jobs like petty trade, food vending, and small businesses. This diversification is in line with households’ attempts to mitigate against seasonal income shortages or cocoa price variability, a risk to livelihood sustainability.

One ward executive officer explained, “*Some of the farmers do kiosks or marketing on local markets when cocoa is off-season.*” Another said, “*women in particular get involved with alternative small businesses such as tailoring or cooked food.*”

These results are consistent with Anang et al. (2022), who identified income diversification as a strategic livelihood adaptation among cocoa growers in Ghana, especially for the purpose of shock absorption and resilience.

Effect of Cocoa Production on The Livelihood Outcomes Among Cocoa Farmers in The Study Area

Model fitness test

The model summary in Table 6, gives the key indicators for testing the overall fit and performance of a binary logistic regression model used to predict factors affecting cocoa production on livelihood among smallholder cocoa farmers. As can be seen from the Omnibus Test of Model Coefficients which reported a chi-square value of 18.47 with probability $p = 0.000$, the covariates including cocoa production-related variables significantly improve the model significance as a whole. Similarly, the Hosmer and Lemeshow Test result ($\chi^2 = 5.216$, $p = 0.735$) which is insignificant confirming that the model fits the data well and there is no significant difference between observed and predicted values. The -2 Log Likelihood value of 284.287 further suggests a relatively strong model fit. These indicators affirm that the model reliably predicts how cocoa production influences livelihood improvements among smallholder farmers.

Table 6: Model Summary and Fitness test

Variable	Coefficient	Sig
Omnibus Test (χ^2)	18.47 (3)	0.000
Hosmer and Lemeshow Test (χ^2)	5.216 (8),	0.735
Pseudo R ² (Cox and Snell R Square)	0.184	
Nagelkerke R Square	0.244	
-2 Log Likelihood	284.287	

Multicollinearity test

The multicollinearity problem was test using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test. Results presented in Table 7 indicated the average value of VIF is 1.913 which is below 5 implying that the analysed data were free from the multicollinearity problem.

Table 7: Multicollinearity tests Results

Variables	Tolerance Value	VIF
Quantity of cocoa produced	0.31	1.43
Size of land owned	0.462	2.863
Price of cocoa	0.340	2.452
Access to Credit	0.278	1.561
Education level	0.224	1.112
Ownership of Farming tools	0.442	2.763
Age of Farmer	0.256	1.212

The study analysed the effects on cocoa production on the smallholder farmers' livelihoods using six indicators which included, quantity of cocoa produced, land size, price od cocoa, access to credit, ownership of farming tools and education level. Following the analysis, results in Table 8 show that, quantity of cocoa produced presented a statistically positive significant relationship with farmers' livelihoods having coefficient of 0.654 with a p-value of 0.003. This implies that, an increase in cocoa production by one unit could contribute the improvement of farmers' livelihood by 65percent. Similarly, the odds ratio of 1.923 implies that a unit increase in cocoa output nearly doubles the likelihood of achieving improved livelihood outcomes among smallholder farmers in Kyela district.

Household land size has positive and statistically significant effect on the livelihoods (coefficient = 0.512, p = 0.010), meaning that households who have a bigger land size increases the likelihood of having better livelihoods by about 51%. This would further imply that; since having a larger holding of land permits, farmers can expand cocoa even in the short term, diversify into crops and amass wealth. This makes land a key variable in the prosperity of rural household.

Table 8: Binary Logistic Regression Results on cocoa production to livelihood outcomes among cocoa farmers

Variables	B	S. E	Sig	Exp(B)
Quantity of cocoa produced (MT)	0.654	0.211	0.003	1.923
Size of land owned (Ha)	0.512	0.197	0.010	1.669
Price of cocoa (TZS)	0.432	0.185	0.021	1.540
Access to Credit (1=Yes,0=No)	0.488	0.196	0.014	1.629
Education level (Years)	0.742	0.225	0.001	2.100
Ownership of Farming tools (1= Yes, 0 = No)	0.391	0.183	0.034	1.479
Age of Farmer (Years)	0.422	0.191	0.024	1.632
Constant	-0.837	0.563	0.138	0.433

Dependent Variable = Livelihood (1 = Improved, 0 = Not Improved)

The price of cocoa (Table 8) also showed a significant positive relation with livelihood outcome with an effect size of 0.432 ($p = 0.021$). This shows that better market prices farmers get increase the odds of having improved livelihood by 43%. A fair and stable cocoa price provides farmers with predictable income to invest in farm expansion and household improvements. This confirms Resell and Prestegard (2024) who reported how stable and premium pricing mechanisms of certified supply chains in Tanzania exert a positive role on the cocoa farmers' perception of sustainability. The above objectives call for strengthening marketing systems and implementing pricing regimes as important policies in the rural welfare improvement.

Results in Table 8 further show that access to credit by farmers had a positive and significant relationship with the livelihood outcomes, with the coefficient 0.488 ($p = 0.014$). This indicates a unit increase in access to financial services like credit could improve livelihood outcome of smallholder by 48%. The odds ratio of 1.629 suggests that the likelihood of credit access to improve the livelihood of farmers is 2 times. This implies that better access to financial services such as credit and remittances significantly enhances the capacity of farmers to acquire advanced agricultural inputs and technology which will contribute to increased production and income.

Regarding to education level by farmers, it indicated that increase in the number years in schooling the farmers has gone, the more likely to improve their wellbeing as indicated by large significant ($p = 0.001$) and strong positive relationship (0.74) with improved livelihood outcomes. The odd ration of 2.10 means that respondents with better education and skills are more than twice likely to achieve improved livelihoods compared to those with lower education level. Such knowledge enables farmers to make informed decisions and the adoption of modern agricultural practices and market conditions. This finding aligns with Carney (1998), who noted that human capital is foundational to enhancing rural productivity and livelihood sustainability. In Kyela, investments in training and education could contribute to more productive farming and diversified income sources.

Farming tools shows a significant positive relationship with livelihood outcomes, with a coefficient of 0.391 ($p = 0.034$). This suggests that access to physical resources such as tractor, infrastructure and other equipment increases the likelihood of farmers to improve their livelihoods by nearly 40%. Additionally, the odd ratio of 1.479 indicates that the

likelihood of farm assets in improving the farmers' livelihood is almost twice times. Adequate physical capital enables farmers to optimize production and reduce losses, thus enhancing their economic resilience. Additionally, age of respondents presented a positive significant effect on farmers livelihood with a coefficient of 0.442 ($p= 0.024$) with odd ratio of 1.6. This implies that the likelihood of elder farmer to improve the life wellbeing from cocoa production is approximately two times as compared to younger farmer. The possible explanation could be the fact that older farmers had accumulative livelihood assets and experiences which enabled him/her to produce more cocoa produce.

Discussion

Analysis of descriptive and demographic results indicated majority of cocoa farmers fallow under active groups implying the continuation of the production activities in the district. Similar results were found by Bannor et al. (2022) who observed that active age groups are more responsive to innovation and business training, which can improve cocoa production and livelihood outcomes. Also, the results support that of Sekiya et al. (2020), who found that age affected farmers' capacity to look for and secure off-farm employment and income, which might boost their income. The coincidence of these findings justifies that agricultural production in Africa and particularly in Tanzania is dominated by youths. The data also coincident with the nation census of 2022 which indicated the youths to occupies the majority (60%) of the population.

On the other hand, famers who are married were found to be likely to be more attached to land productivity and household welfare, which affect the prospects of cocoa farming as a livelihood. As Hainmueller, Hiscox, and Tampe (2011) have noted that marital status is linked to household stability and labor availability thus promoting participation in agricultural development program. Farmers with higher education wre found to participate more in modern production technologies and therefore produced more outputs. This aid them in production and advertising policy making. Farmers with higher education are to easily adopt sustainable practices and diversify income sources (Asare et al., 2020). Therefore, implantation of strategies focused on enhancing educational support in farming communities could thus increase cocoa productivity and thus livelihoods.

The impact of cocoa production on the smallholder framers' livelihoods in Kyela district were influenced by quality of cocoa produced. The positive associations between livelihood and cocoa production indicate the critical role played by the crop in the life of people. In general, the results suggest that higher yields in cocoa production directly enhance household income and capacity to meet essential needs such as education, food, and housing. These findings concur with those of Mwambene (2021), which emphasized that increased cocoa productivity in Mbeya significantly boosts household income levels. This indicate that, investing in advanced production farming practices such as application of improved fertilizers, seeds and pest control will enhance cocoa productivity and thus leads to broader improvements in farmer wellbeing.

Land size allocated on cocoa production and price received by smallholder farmers were the catalyst to livelihood improvement. Large land size could imply more outputs will be produced and if these outputs are sold at high price will attract more income

farmers which will be used in acquiring livelihood assets. This result confirms the findings of Lazaro and Makindara (2020) that landholding is a strong predictor of cocoa profitability in Kyela. Similar to that of Akamagwuna and Nwosu (2021) in Nigeria that land size directly affected the cocoa production and productivity for smallholder farmers. The results also confirm that of Resell and Prestegard (2024) who reported how stable and premium pricing mechanisms of certified supply chains in Tanzania exert a positive role on the cocoa farmers' perception of sustainability. The lesson may be that, in order to increase the productivity and security of farming households, policies promoting equal access to land as well as formal land rights are needed. The above objectives call for strengthening marketing systems and implementing pricing regimes as important policies in the rural welfare improvement.

Moreover, farmers with more access to credit were found to be more productive as access to credit enabled increase their purchasing power on improved agricultural inputs. The use of improved agricultural technologies by farmers led to more cocoa outputs and income earned. These results are consistent with those of Fountain and Huetz-Adams (2020), who emphasized that access to stable and sufficient financial resources improves the resilience and welfare of cocoa farming households particularly in developing countries. Therefore, access to financial resources is the key factor for livelihood transformation in cocoa-growing areas like Kyela district. The findings mirror those of Oomes et al. (2016), who found that physical assets play a critical role in improving productivity and reducing vulnerabilities in cocoa-producing households. In the same vein, ownership of farm implements such as tractor, ploughs and irrigation scheme indicated to improve the livelihood for smallholder farmers through increased income from cocoa production. In general, better access to tools and storage facilities is key to achieving sustained income and food security in Kyela.

The age of farmers presents a positive significant relation with the livelihoods among smallholder farmers. The positive effect of age on farmers' livelihood indicate that an elder farmer has more accumulation of livelihoods assets and experience which enable him/her to purchasing agricultural inputs and adoption of modern technologies in the production and marketing activities, which could contribute on the increase in productivity and outputs from cocoa production. The increases in the quantity of cocoa produced could imply that more cocoa will be sold to the market, leading to more income earned by farmers. The increased income generated from cocoa production can be used to acquire more livelihood assets such as income and food security to improve their livelihoods. These findings support the argument by Natarajan et al. (2022) that accumulation of more livelihood assets among farmers in the rural setting could contribute on the improvement of their income, education and wellbeing. The same findings were reported by ICCO (2025) that increased income from cocoa production increased the farmers' access to agricultural inputs, education and healthcare.

Conclusions

The study investigated the contribution of cocoa production to the improved livelihoods of smallholder farmers in Kyela District, Mbeya Region. From the descriptive results, cocoa farming is important for these farmers as source of livelihood, they are mostly engaged in agriculture as their major occupation. The high proportion of

the variance explained by larger land owned, more education obtained, cocoa yield and price, as well as use of financial services reflects the observation that these are key factors contributing positively to improve livelihood.

These findings imply that enhancements in cocoa productivity and stable, attractive pricing lead to higher levels of farm household income, improved food security, and greater access to vital social services like education and health. Furthermore, land ownership is critically important for farmers to expand production and also price stability the consistent income that allows for both investment and everyday spending. In conclusion, cocoa production is a strong engine of socio-economic development among the smallholder farmers in Kyela District, which indicates its significance in rural development policies.

Policy Recommendations

Drawing on the results of study, it is recommended that government and other actors in cocoa production should do more by educating farmers on good farming practices and improving access to financial services for farmer with the establishment of flexible credit scheme while designing loans that fit into cooperative as well as SMEs. This would facilitate the capacity of farmers to secure sophisticated agricultural inputs and technology for enhanced productivity level and livelihood. Furthermore, agricultural training programs, farmer field schools and extension services need to be strengthened and extended throughout the Kyela District so as to empower farmers with the appropriate knowledge/skill that is required for enhancing productivity in order to improve livelihood resilience.

Limitation and future studies

Cross-sectional data were applied to draw this conclusion in the present study. The use of cross-sectional data in estimating the effect of cocoa production on the livelihoods of smallholder farmers in the study area is a limitation, since it does not account for long term implications of cocoa farming. A cross-sectional view provides a momentary exposure and may not consider dynamic tendencies or seasonal/structural differences. Again, the study was carried out in only one district to estimate the cocoa production effect on livelihood. Thus, future research should attempt to use time series data and include more regions/districts so that a more complete picture of short-term fluctuations as well as long-term trends in cocoa production can be drawn to better understand their consequences for farmer livelihood.

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<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Maziku, P. Kabipi and Mwambeso, T. K. (2026). Cocoa Production and Rural Livelihood Outcomes: A Sustainable Livelihood Framework and Binary Regression Analysis among Smallholder Farmers. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 13(1), 56-79. doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2025.557370.1885</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_236925.html</p>	A square QR code that, when scanned, likely leads to the full article page.